

UNLOCK YOUR VOICE: IMPLEMENTING WRITE, RISE, AND RESPOND TECHNIQUE IN REDUCING THE FEAR OF MAKING ORAL MISTAKES TO SECOND LANGUAGE

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Available Online: March 2025
Revised: January 2025
Accepted: January 2025
Received: February 2025

Volume III Issue 1 (2025)
DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.15030989
E-ISSN: 2984-7184
P-ISSN: 2984-7176
<https://getinternational.org/research/>

Abstract

One of the most significant challenges encountered by language learners is the fear of making mistakes, especially when speaking. This study evaluated the effectiveness of the Write, Rise, and Respond (WRR) technique in reducing learners' fear of making oral mistakes. The WRR technique involves writing thoughts, sharing them when ready which requires standing, and receiving constructive feedback from teachers to foster a supportive learning environment. A quasi-experimental design using quantitative data collection, including means and t-tests, was employed. Ten (10) Grade 11 students from the Humanities and Social Sciences (HUMSS) strand enrolled at Immaculate Conception College of Balayan Inc. for the Academic Year 2023-2024 were selected through purposive sampling. A Likert scale survey measured their fear levels. Over a three-week period, results revealed a statistically significant reduction in fear, with a general weighted mean of 3.45 for pre-activity and a general weighted mean of 1.75 for post-activity, respectively ($p < 0.05$). The WRR technique effectively reduced fear and enhanced confidence among Grade 11 HUMSS students, demonstrating its potential as a valuable tool in education. Building on these findings, future research could explore support programs like confidence-building workshops and one-on-one counseling, while also examining the long-term impact and broader applicability of the WRR technique across diverse student groups and educational settings.

Keywords: *Fear, Oral Mistakes, and Write, Rise, and Respond (WRR) technique*

Recommended Citation:

Grubat, G. B., Ila, K. V. T., Alaras, M. R. V., Angelo, A. A. E., Banaag, R. A. A., Velasco, M. A. E., Rival, J. M., & Mangarin, J. A. (2025). UNLOCK YOUR VOICE: IMPLEMENTING WRITE, RISE, AND RESPOND TECHNIQUE IN REDUCING THE FEAR OF MAKING ORAL MISTAKES TO SECOND LANGUAGE. GUILD OF EDUCATORS IN TESOL INTERNATIONAL RESEARCH JOURNAL, 3(1), 74–84. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15030989>

INTRODUCTION

The Philippines was one of the most linguistically diverse countries because of its various languages and dialects. In fact, the Philippines had two official languages: English and Filipino. These two official languages upheld the country's historical background from diverse cultural influences. Filipino, primarily based on the Tagalog dialect, was the national language and the symbol of unity among the nation. English, on the other hand, held significant prominence in education as the main medium of instruction, especially in science, technology, and math. It was also used as a primary language in businesses, government, and international communication. Additionally, English-speaking proficiency was considered one of the country's strengths, helping the economy and establishing the Philippines as a leading global destination for voice outsourcing, as stated by Cabigon (2015).

Moreover, the International Education Center recently administered an English proficiency ranking test across all countries, and the Philippines showed slight improvement, ranking 20th out of 113 countries in the 2023 EPI, up from 22nd among 111 in the 2022 EPI (Marcelo, 2023). Despite the minor increase in the Philippines' ranking, there were still major factors affecting English learners' proficiency. According to the study by Cervantes (2023), the Philippines' new agency conducted a pool survey, which revealed that only 55 percent of participants were English proficient. However, this also meant that nearly half of the Filipino people struggled in learning English as a foreign language, as they faced various challenges along the way.

Furthermore, many studies discussed the challenges that caused English learners to struggle. Specifically, Arifin's (2017) study highlighted that fear of making mistakes was a natural problem among English learners in speaking classes, hindering language development. Madill's (2016) study stated that fear of making mistakes often developed depending on how peers perceived learners inside the classroom. Students often perceived their peers' judgment of their speaking skills as a source of pressure to deliver their message, potentially due to extreme nervousness about making mistakes.

On the other hand, in recent years, the country had to increase its efforts to enhance the instruction of English-speaking skills, cultivating them as an essential skill, based on the agreement of stakeholders (Cabigon, 2015). Consequently, Maquidato's (2021) study suggested that future researchers could conduct a quasi-experimental study to identify strategies for reducing the fear of mistakes in L2 production and expression among 21st-century students.

With this, the researchers of this study aimed to implement a technique, specifically the "Write, Rise, and Respond" technique, which was used as an intervention for a three-week experimental process to address and reduce the fear of making oral mistakes among selected Grade 11 students from Our Lady of Miraculous Medal under the Humanities and Social Sciences Strand, enrolled at Immaculate Conception College of Balayan Inc. for the Academic Year 2023-2024. This technique entailed second-language learners expressing their thoughts through writing, standing up to share their ideas when they were ready, and receiving constructive feedback from teachers who promoted active listening among peers, creating a supportive and positive environment that nurtured growth. It was intended to help learners overcome their fear of making oral mistakes in the English language by actively engaging with the language in various ways, facilitating language acquisition.

Objectives

This study aims to determine the effectiveness of implementing the Write, Rise, and Respond technique in reducing learners' fear of making oral mistakes. Specifically, the study aimed to address the following questions:

1. What is the level of the respondents' fear of making oral mistakes in terms of:
 - 1.1. pre-activity; and
 - 1.2. post-activity
2. What are causes of the selected respondents' fear of making oral mistakes to second language?
3. How does the implementation of the Write, Rise, and Respond technique contribute in improving confidence in oral performance among the respondents?
4. Is there a significant difference between the level of fear of making oral mistakes in terms of pre-activity and post-activity?

METHODS

Methodology and Design

To address the primary objective of the study, the researchers employed a quasi-experimental design within a quantitative research framework, focusing on quantifying data analysis and collection. In relevance, Maquidato's (2021) study suggested that future researchers conduct quasi-experimental studies to identify strategies for reducing fear of mistakes in second-language (L2) production and expression among 21st-century students. This recommendation provided the foundation for the researchers to undertake this study. Using a quasi-experimental design, the researchers gathered precise, accurate, and detailed information for statistical analysis, allowing them to reliably assess the effectiveness of the WRR technique in reducing learners' fear of making oral mistakes.

Population and Sampling

The population of this study included ten (10) selected respondents from one section of the Grade 11 - Humanities and Social Sciences (HUMSS) strand at Immaculate Conception College, A.Y. 2023-2024, identified through purposive sampling under a non-probability sampling method.

Instrumentations

To accomplish the main objective of this research study, the researchers utilized a survey, specifically a Likert scale, to gather data. This approach aimed to measure the opinions, attitudes, and behaviors of selected respondents from one section of the Grade 11 - Humanities and Social Sciences (HUMSS) strand. According to Maruf (2023), a Likert scale typically consists of a statement or question followed by a range of responses indicating the degree to which the respondent agrees or disagrees. In this study, responses were worded on a 4-point scale, including the following options: "Always/Strongly Agree"; "Sometimes/Agree"; "Seldom/Disagree"; and "Never/Strongly Disagree."

Data Collection

To accomplish the objectives of the study, the following steps were undertaken. First, a letter of request was sent to the class advisers of all the Grade 11 sections under the Humanities and Social Sciences strand to request the selection of respondents. Upon receiving approval, the researchers formulated a set of speaking indicators to be used as the observational tool, which was then evaluated by the research adviser. After receiving approval, these indicators were communicated to the respondents, and a three-day observation period was conducted for each section to identify individuals who met the predetermined criteria established by the researchers.

Subsequently, after obtaining the results, the researchers sought referrals from the class advisers and core subject teachers, specifically those teaching Oral Communication, to identify ten (10) students who were academically

skilled but demonstrated insufficient participation during class. The collected data was kept confidential and intended solely for research purposes. The results of the data were tallied and submitted for statistical analysis.

Data Analysis

With the focal questions in mind and with the aim to analyze the data, the researchers applied the appropriate statistical treatments. The data gathered were tallied and tabulated, and the specified statistical treatments were applied as follows:

1. Weighted Mean. This was used to analyze the level of fear reported by respondents both before (pre-activity) and after (post-activity) engaging in the Write, Rise, and Respond (WRR) Strategy. It was also used to identify the causes of the fear of making oral mistakes in the second language among the respondents and to assess the impact of the WRR technique on their confidence.
2. T-tests. These were used to determine if there was a significant difference between the respondents' level of fear of making oral mistakes before (pre-activity) and after (post-activity) engaging in the WRR technique.

Ethical Consideration

As part of the ethical considerations of this study, the researchers adhered to the code of conduct to ensure the protection of respondents' rights and the rights of those involved. Measures were taken to guarantee that the study was conducted in an appropriate and ethical manner. To ensure compliance with ethical standards, letters were submitted to the administration's office, and the process was explained to the class adviser and the selected respondents. Consent forms were distributed to ensure informed participation. The consent form, which served as a guideline for the research and consent process, can be found in Appendix A. The researchers made every effort to protect the privacy and safety of the respondents and all individuals involved.

Results and Discussion

Table 1

Interpretation of Pre-Activity Data in Determining the Level of Fear on making Oral Mistakes among selected learners of Grade 11 – HUMSS

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Interpretation	Rank
1. I speak in low volume for people not to hear my voice.	3.40	Always	6
2. I tend to avoid establishing eye contact when speaking towards others.	2.90	Sometimes	10
3. I often silently criticize myself for committing mistakes when communicating.	3.20	Sometimes	9
4. I tend to stay quiet during class discussions or group works.	3.50	Always	4
5. I am hesitant in asking questions in class for I am afraid that I may sound foolish to others.	3.80	Always	2
6. I do not volunteer in class presentations and speech deliveries.	3.30	Always	8
7. I struggle in clearly articulating my thoughts and ideas when using English language.	3.40	Always	6
8. I feel pressured when I am using English language for speaking purposes, thus this hinders my ability to interact.	3.70	Always	3

9. My self-confidence decreases when I am committing mistakes in speaking using English.	3.40	Always	6
10. I use filler words (e.g., um, uh) excessively when speaking due to nervousness.	3.90	Always	1
General Weighted Mean	3.45	Always	

In terms of pre-activity, a deep understanding of the patterns and variables that influence the level of fear of making oral mistakes from one section of the Grade 11 - Humanities and Social Sciences (HUMSS) strand, highlights the need for focused support and interventions. For instance, respondents agreed that they use filler words (e.g., um, uh) excessively when speaking due to nervousness, with the highest weighted mean of 3.90, indicating a verbal interpretation of "Always". The data implies that due to nervousness, the excessive use of filler words was "Always" observed to the respondents most during pre-activity.

In relevance, Abdullah et al. (2022) noted in their study that the excessive use of filler words is common to those individuals who are experiencing anxiety while speaking. In this study, it was emphasized that it is one of the significant impacts of language learning anxiety on oral performance, that reflects to the feelings of tension, nervousness, and fear. With a verbal interpretation of "Always," the general weighted mean of 3.45 indicates that students typically experience these anxieties and concerns regularly. This result provides valuable guidance for addressing and aiding students in overcoming these challenges effectively.

Table 2

Interpretation of Post-Activity Data in Determining the Level of Fear on making Oral Mistakes among selected learners of Grade 11 – HUMSS

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Interpretation	Rank
1. I speak in low volume for people not to hear my voice.	1.60	Never	7
2. I tend to avoid establishing eye contact when speaking towards others.	2.10	Seldom	2
3. I often silently criticize myself for committing mistakes when communicating.	2.10	Seldom	2
4. I tend to stay quiet during class discussions or group works.	1.60	Never	7
5. I am hesitant in asking questions in class for I am afraid that I may sound foolish to others.	1.50	Never	9.5
6. I do not volunteer in class presentations and speech deliveries.	1.50	Never	9.5
7. I struggle in clearly articulating my thoughts and ideas when using English language.	1.80	Seldom	5
8. I feel pressured when I am using English language for speaking purposes, thus this hinders my ability to interact.	2	Seldom	4
9. My self-confidence decreases when I am committing mistakes in speaking using English.	1.60	Never	7
10. I use filler words (e.g., um, uh) excessively when speaking due to nervousness.	2.10	Seldom	2
General Weighted Mean	1.79	Seldom	

The post-activity results revealed a significant improvement in students' fear of making oral mistakes following the three-week implementation of the Write, Rise, and Respond (WRR) technique. For instance, respondents agreed that they seldom avoided eye contact when speaking, as shown by a weighted mean of 2.10. This shift indicates an enhancement in the students' confidence, as they became more comfortable making eye contact with their audience or listeners. The WRR technique supports this improvement by fostering a safe and constructive learning environment where students can receive feedback. This aligns with Kirkham's (2023) study, which emphasizes the importance of rehearsing speeches to achieve clarity on key points. Preparing and practicing speeches boosts learners' confidence, enabling them to maintain better eye contact during delivery.

Moreover, the respondents generally agreed that they seldom silently criticizing themselves for making mistakes during communication, also with a weighted mean of 2.10. This finding demonstrates progress in how students manage oral mistakes through the WRR technique. The approach aligns with the study of Jamrus et al. (2019), which highlights the value of self-assessment and reflection in improving speaking skills. By allowing students to evaluate their performance, they become more adept at handling errors and improving their overall communication abilities.

In addition, Indicator No. 10, along with Indicators 2 and 3, ranked highest in the survey. It revealed that respondents seldom used filler words such as "um" and "uh" when speaking due to nervousness, reflected in a weighted mean of 2.10. This improvement can be attributed to the WRR technique, which provides students with time to prepare and rehearse their responses. This preparation reduced their dependence on filler words, enhancing their fluency and confidence. Similarly, Bartram (2023) supports this finding, noting that preparation and rehearsal help minimize the use of fillers, promoting more polished and effective speech delivery.

Overall, the general weighted mean of 1.79, verbally interpreted as "Seldom," indicates substantial progress in reducing nervous habits and improving communication skills among Grade 11 Humanities and Social Sciences (HUMSS) students. This contrasts with the pre-activity results, where excessive use of filler words was observed "Always," with the highest weighted mean of 3.90. This comparison underscores the effectiveness of the WRR technique in addressing students' oral communication challenges, reflecting that the respondents have made significant progress in managing the fear that they have for oral mistakes after following a three-week experimentation period.

Table 3

Verbal Interpretation of Data in Determining Causes of Fear of Making Oral Mistakes to Second Language of selected learners from Grade 11 – HUMSS

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Interpretation	Rank
1. I experience fear of embarrassment when I speak English.	3.4	Strongly Agree	4
2. I lack in confidence when showcasing my language skills.	3.4	Strongly Agree	4
3. I have a weak foundation in the English language.	3.1	Agree	9.5
4. Perfectionist tendencies influence my speaking in English.	3.7	Strongly Agree	1
5. I feel pressure from my peers to utilize English language perfectly.	3.4	Strongly Agree	4
6. I have limited English vocabulary.	3.3	Strongly Agree	6
7. I struggle with unfamiliarity on grammar and sentence structure when speaking English.	3.6	Strongly Agree	2

8. I feel afraid of mispronouncing words when speaking English in front of others.	3.1	Agree	9.5
9. I face criticism for my fluency in speaking English due to my lack of familiarity with English-speaking environments.	3.2	Agree	7.5
10. I am afraid of committing mistakes and creating negative impressions to my audience when using English language.	3.2	Agree	7.5
General Weighted Mean	3.34	Strongly Agree	

The indicator "Perfectionist tendencies influence my speaking in English" emerged as the highest-ranking factor, with a weighted mean of 3.70 and a verbal interpretation of "Strongly Agree." This finding reveals that respondents commonly set exceptionally high standards for themselves, which adversely affects their ability to speak in English. Huang (2022) supports this observation, noting that the intense pressure perfectionist individuals experience in striving for English-speaking proficiency often leads to heightened anxiety during the language learning process.

Perfectionism in language learning is further characterized by traits closely linked to other behavioral conditions, making it a significant factor in understanding language-related challenges. In relation to the fear of making oral mistakes, an overall weighted mean of 3.34, also interpreted as "Strongly Agree," was recorded among selected Grade 11 Humanities and Social Sciences (HUMSS) students. This result emphasizes that personal experiences and the pressures of language learning play a substantial role in their fear of making mistakes, highlighting the need for focused interventions to address these concerns.

Table 4

Verbal Interpretation of Data in Determining Impact of Write, Rise, and Respond Technique on the Confidence of selected respondents from one section of the Grade 11 - Humanities and Social Sciences (HUMSS) strand.

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Interpretation	Rank
1. I feel encouraged to speak without the fear of making mistakes, specifically in oral communication.	3.70	Strongly Agree	2
2. I believe that my oral communication skills have improved since implementing this technique.	3.70	Strongly Agree	2
3. I feel safe and encouraged to experiment with language and express myself orally.	3.40	Strongly Agree	6.5
4. I find myself more willing to engage in spontaneous conversations, knowing I can speak without fear of judgment.	3.20	Agree	9
5. I notice a decrease in fear related to making oral mistakes in the second language.	3.60	Strongly Agree	4.5
6. I feel more comfortable participating in group discussions or conversations with other people in the second language.	3.30	Strongly Agree	8
7. I am able to effectively convey my thoughts and ideas in the second language without being hindered by the fear of making mistakes.	3.10	Agree	10
8. I am more willing to take risks and try out new vocabulary or grammar structures in my conversations.	3.70	Strongly Agree	2
9. I feel more confident in my ability to speak without fear of making mistakes, leading to an increased willingness to participate in language activities.	3.60	Strongly Agree	4.5

10. I experience less nervousness when speaking in front of others, enabling me to engage more actively in oral interactions.	3.40	Strongly Agree	6.5
General Weighted Mean	3.47	Strongly Agree	

Several key indicators highlight the effectiveness of the Write, Rise, and Respond (WRR) technique in improving oral communication skills among respondents. Indicator No. 8, "I am more willing to take risks and try out new vocabulary or grammar structures in my conversations," ranks highest with a weighted mean of 3.70, verbally interpreted as "Strongly Agree." This result reflects the respondents' general willingness to take risks in practicing a second language. The WRR technique fosters this by providing constructive feedback and a safe learning environment, aligning with Riasati's (2018) findings that confidence-building and risk-taking are essential for effective language learning.

Similarly, Indicator No. 2, "I believe that my oral communication skills have improved since implementing this technique," also ranks highest with a weighted mean of 3.70. This demonstrates that respondents perceive significant improvement in their speaking skills and reduced fear of oral mistakes after the implementation of the WRR technique. Zoubi (2018) emphasizes the importance of sufficient practice and exposure to the target language, which the WRR technique effectively facilitates.

Indicator No. 1, "I feel encouraged to speak without the fear of making mistakes, specifically in oral communication," also shares the highest rank with a weighted mean of 3.70. This result highlights the respondents' increased self-confidence and reduced fear of making mistakes, further supported by the WRR technique's structured practice sessions. Kirkham (2023) underscores that providing students with opportunities to rehearse and refine their speech builds confidence and enhances their ability to communicate effectively in the target language.

Above all, in terms of determining the impact of the Write, Rise, and Respond (WRR) technique on the confidence of the selected respondents from one section of the Grade 11 - Humanities and Social Sciences (HUMSS) strand, an overall weighted mean of 3.47 with a verbal interpretation of "Always", was gathered. This result proves that the Write, Rise, and Respond (WRR) technique was highly effective in terms of reducing the fear of making oral mistakes and enhancing the confidence of the respondents of the study.

Table 5
Verbal Interpretation of Data in Determining the Significant Difference in terms of the Pre-Activity and Post-Activity

	MEAN	SD	t- value	p- value	Decision on Ho Interpretation
Pre- Activity	3.45	0.207	15.4	<0.001	Reject Ho
Post- Activity	1.79	0.233			Significant

Significant at p < 0.05

Table 5 revealed that there is a significant difference between the Pre-Activity and Post-Activity results in terms of the level of fear of making oral mistakes among the selected respondents from one section of the Grade 11 – Humanities and Social Sciences (HUMSS) strand, following a three-week experimentation period. With p-value of less than 0.05 ($p < 0.05$), this indicates a meaningful disparity between the pre-test and post-test scores which leads to the initial null hypothesis to be rejected.

The findings reveal a significant reduction in students' fear of making mistakes during oral activities after the implementation of the Write, Rise, and Respond technique. The Pre-Activity results show a general weighted mean of 3.45, which decreased to 1.79 in the Post-Activity results. This demonstrates the effectiveness of the technique in alleviating students' concerns about making errors while speaking.

Similarly, Ariska's (2019) study emphasizes the importance of employing strategic techniques to enhance students' speaking skills. Ariska's findings suggest that these techniques not only improve speaking proficiency but also encourage students to prepare beforehand, thus reducing language anxiety. In the same way, the Write, Rise, and Respond technique follows similar principles, allowing students adequate time to write and rehearse their responses before speaking. This preparation helps minimize their fear of making mistakes during oral activities.

CONCLUSION

Based on the gathered and interpreted data, the following conclusions are drawn:

The findings presented in Table 3 highlight the level of fear of making oral mistakes among selected Grade 11 Humanities and Social Sciences (HUMSS) students during the pre-activity stage. This underscores the critical need for targeted support and interventions to address these challenges.

Following a three-week experimentation period, the data in Table 4 demonstrate significant progress in managing the fear of making oral mistakes among the same group of respondents during the post-activity stage. This improvement suggests the effectiveness of the interventions applied.

Meanwhile, Table 5 provides insights into the causes of fear in making oral mistakes in a second language. For Grade 11 HUMSS learners, these fears are primarily rooted in personal experiences and the inherent challenges of language acquisition, which significantly impact their English fluency.

The results in Table 6 reveal the positive impact of the Write, Rise, and Respond (WRR) technique. Its implementation among Grade 11 HUMSS learners has proven to be highly effective in building their confidence, further supporting its value as an instructional strategy.

Finally, Table 7 highlights a significant difference between the pre-activity and post-activity levels of fear of making oral mistakes among the same students. This finding underscores the measurable success of the interventions and the WRR technique in addressing students' concerns and enhancing their oral communication skills.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings and conclusion of the study, the following are formulated and hereby recommended:

The findings of Table 3 presents the interpretation of pre-activity data in determining the level of fear of making oral mistakes among selected Grade 11 – HUMSS respondents. Future researchers could create support programs to address this fear, including confidence-building workshops, one-on-one counseling, and practice sessions in a safe and supportive environment.

Table 4 presents the interpretation of post-activity data in determining the level of fear of making oral mistakes among selected Grade 11 – HUMSS respondents. Since this study focused on pre- and post-activities, future researchers could expand on this by analyzing daily assessment results and students' responses per session. This approach would

provide a more detailed understanding of day-to-day progress and the specific aspects of the technique that are most effective.

Table 5 provides the verbal interpretation of data in determining the causes of fear of making oral mistakes in a second language among the selected Grade 11 – HUMSS respondents. Future researchers could explore students' detailed personal experiences and specific challenges in learning a second language through qualitative methods such as interviews or focus groups.

Table 6 presents the verbal interpretation of data in determining the impact of the Write, Rise, and Respond (WRR) technique on the confidence of selected Grade 11 – HUMSS respondents. Future research could examine how effective the WRR technique is with different groups of students and in various educational settings. Researchers could also analyze different components of the WRR technique to identify which aspects contribute most to boosting students' confidence.

Table 7 provides the verbal interpretation of data in determining the significant difference between pre-activity and post-activity results. Future researchers could conduct long-term studies to assess whether the improvements are sustained over time. Additionally, they could investigate which aspects of the intervention had the greatest impact, allowing for further refinement and broader application of the technique.

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